

Studies on the Effect of Ultra-violet Light on Colloids. Part II.

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In a previous paper (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 6, 547) the effect of ultra-violet light on a number of colloidal solutions has been studied, and it was found that in a majority of cases coagulation resulted. It has been shown that the coagulation of colloids by ultra-violet radiations can be satisfactorily explained on the basis of slow chemical and photochemical changes brought about by light. In the present paper a number of other colloidal solutions have been studied.

EXPERIMENTAL.

A series of both positively and negatively charged colloidal solutions of silver salts were prepared by Lottermoser's process (*J. pr. Chem.*, 1905, ii, 72, 39). The sols were divided into two parts, one kept in the dark and the other exposed to ultra-violet light. All the sols on exposure were coagulated. The colloidal solutions kept in the dark were filtered through an ultra-filter, and the hydrogen-ion concentration of the clear filtrate was determined (*vide* Table I). The following sols were studied.

Silver Iodide Sol.

2 C.c. of 0.1N-silver nitrate were added drop by drop, with constant stirring to 100 c.c. of 0.003N-potassium iodide, whereby a clear yellowish sol was obtained. The sol was *negatively* charged and contained 0.0235 g. of silver iodide per c.c.

A positively charged silver iodide sol was also prepared by adding gradually 2 c.c. of 0.1N-potassium iodide to 100 c.c. of 0.003N-silver nitrate. The resulting *positively* charged sol also contained 0.0235 g. of silver iodide per c.c. Both the positively and negatively charged sols were coagulated on exposure to ultra-violet light, and the p_H values of the filtrates were determined (Table I).

TABLE I.

Sol.	pH (unexposed).	pH (exposed).
Positive silver iodide	6.78	4.50
Negative silver iodide	6.89	6.80
Positive silver arsenate	6.45	6.00
Positive silver thiocyanate	5.74	5.10
Silver (by tannin)	6.90	9.48
Silver (Carey Lea)	5.90	5.60
Vanadium pentoxide	5.28	7.12
Arsenic sulphide (negative)	4.46	3.23
Arsenic sulphide (positive)	5.26	2.32

Silver Arsenate and Silver Thiocyanate Sols.

Positively charged sols of the above substances were prepared by Lottermöser's process (*loc. cit.*). All the sols were of approximately the same concentration and contained 1.08 g. silver per 100 c.c. (Table I).

Metallic Sols.

A colloidal solution of gold was prepared by reducing 20 c.c. of boiling 0.001% solution of gold chloride by the addition of a few drops of 1% solution of tannic acid. A deep red coloured sol was obtained. A colloidal solution of silver was prepared by adding a few drops of a 1% tannic acid solution and 10% potassium carbonate solution to 100 c.c. of a 0.001N-silver nitrate solution. On warming, a deep reddish-brown sol was obtained. A Carey Lea's silver sol was also prepared by reducing a silver nitrate solution by a mixture of ferrous sulphate and sodium citrate. The sol was purified by repeated precipitation with ammonium nitrate and was finally stabilised by washing. On exposure to ultra-violet light the gold was practically unaffected. Both the silver sols, however, were easily coagulated (Table I).

Hydroxide Sols.

A colloidal solution of vanadium pentoxide was prepared by triturating solid ammonium vanadate with dilute hydrochloric acid and subsequent washing (Biltz, *Ber.*, 1904, 37, 1098). A deep red sol was obtained which, however, could not be dialysed as it tended

to precipitate on dialysis. A colloidal solution of molybdenum blue was obtained by reducing an acidified solution of ammonium molybdate with sulphuretted hydrogen. The sol was dialysed till free from electrolytes. On exposure, the vanadium pentoxide sol set to a dense gel having a bright silky appearance. The molybdenum blue sol was found difficult to coagulate (Table I).

Arsenic Sulphide Sols.

To 100 c.c. of a 0.25% solution of arsenious acid 0.5 c.c. of 1% thorium nitrate solution was added and a slow stream of sulphuretted hydrogen was passed whereby a positively charged arsenic sulphide sol was obtained. A negatively charged sol of arsenic sulphide of the same concentration was prepared from a 0.25% solution of arsenious acid. The two oppositely charged sols were exposed side by side. Both the sols coagulated but the rate of coagulation of the two oppositely charged sols was not the same: the negatively charged sol coagulated first, whereas the positively charged sol coagulated after a further exposure of several hours.

Discussion of Results.

Crowther (*Phil. Mag.*, 1929, 7, 86), who has made an extensive study of the effect of X-radiations on colloids, has come to the conclusion that only sols in which the particles are positively charged are coagulated by X-rays, whereas negatively charged sols remain invariably unaffected. The principle underlying the above generalisation by Crowther, if it be extended to the case of the action of ultra-violet radiations on hydrosols, requires that only sols with a certain sign of charge should be affected by ultra-violet radiations, whereas an oppositely charged one should remain unchanged. Experimental results, however, run quite contrary to the above rule.

Lottermoser's silver sols, which are particularly suitable for the present purpose, as the sign of the charge on the particle can be changed at will, by using an excess of either the silver salt or of the other reacting substance, have all been found to coagulate on exposure to light. Thus both positively as well as negatively charged colloidal solutions of the iodide, arsenate, and thiocyanate of silver, when exposed to radiations under identical conditions, were all precipitated at about the same rate. This shows beyond doubt that

the coagulating effect of ultra-violet light is not limited to colloids with a particular sign of charge. The same result is obtained in the case of arsenious sulphide sol. Negatively charged arsenious sulphide, as prepared by the usual method is easily coagulated by light. When the sign of the charge was reversed by thorium nitrate, the resulting positively charged arsenious sulphide sol was also coagulated on exposure to radiations. A negatively charged gold sol, prepared by reduction with tannic acid, and a negatively charged sol of molybdenum blue were practically unchanged even after considerable exposure.

In the previous paper (*loc. cit.*) we also obtained marked coagulation with positively charged cerium and thorium hydroxide sols and failed to obtain any appreciable coagulation with negatively charged silver sols prepared by Kohlschütter's method (*Z. Elektro-chem.*, 1908, 14, 49) and with negatively charged gum mastic sol. In view of all these experimental results, any explanation of the coagulation of colloids by radiations involving neutralisation of the charge either on the colloid particles or on the ions in the diffuse double layer, seems untenable.

On the other hand, the entire question of coagulation of colloids by radiations can be satisfactorily explained on the basis of the photochemical decomposition of the stabiliser. The coagulation observed with Lottermoser's silver sols lends considerable support to the above view. From the experimental results, it is seen that positively charged sols of the iodide, arsenate, and thiocyanate of silver develop increased acidity on exposure to ultra-violet light. The stability as well the sign of the charge in the case of the above sols, is due to the presence of an excess of silver nitrate in the system, which on exposure to light undergoes a photochemical decomposition, generating traces of nitric acid. The resulting increase in the value of the hydrogen-ion concentration after exposure, is due to this free acid. On the other hand a negatively charged silver iodide sol of the same concentration, on exposure to light, became less acidic, this being due to the small amounts of potassium hydroxide produced by the photochemical decomposition of the potassium iodide (Ross, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1906, 28, 786), an excess of which has to be used for the preparation of the sol.

Carey Lea's silver sol gets coagulated on exposure to light. This sol showed a marked photophoresis, the sol being coagulated on the side of the quartz tube nearest to the mercury lamp, forming a dark shining mirror. Positively charged silver iodide sol prepared by

Lottermoser's method showed a similar photophoresis, but the deposit in this case was formed on the side away from the mercury lamp. Negatively charged silver iodide sol did not show any photophoresis.

Photochemical Changes Induced in Colloid Systems.

During the course of the present investigation we have studied the cases of two colloidal solutions in detail, *vis.*, (1) the coagulation of a silver sol stabilised by tannic acid and (2) the coagulation of a colloidal solution of thorium hydroxide prepared by the dialysis of a thorium nitrate solution.

Thorium Hydroxide Sol.

In the previous paper it was found that the p_H value of a thorium hydroxide sol increased on exposure to ultra-violet light. It was suggested that the above change in the p_H value was due mainly to the photochemical decomposition of nitric acid, which is the stabilising agent for this hydroxide sol.

To verify the above view experimentally, an approximately $N/500$ -solution of nitric acid was exposed in a quartz tube to a mercury vapour lamp. The same solution was taken in another quartz tube into which a piece of platinised platinum foil ($5'' \times 1''$) was introduced and the whole system was exposed to ultra-violet light. The platinised platinum foil was carefully purified from any adsorbed electrolytes by repeated washing with and electrolysis in distilled water. The p_H values of both the exposed nitric acid solutions were compared with that of the same nitric acid solution kept in the dark. The p_H values were measured with a quinhydrone electrode, which has been found quite suitable for measuring the hydrogen-ion concentration of nitric acid solutions (Billmann, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1924, 19, 876). The following readings were obtained:—

Nitric acid (unexposed)	...	...	...	$p_H 2.92$
Nitric acid (exposed)	...	...	...	3.00
Nitric acid (exposed with platinum)	...	...	...	3.19

Though the photochemical decomposition of moderately concentrated aqueous nitric acid is well known, very dilute solutions of nitric acid are not easily acted upon by light (Berthelot, *Compt. rend.*, 1898, 127, 148).

The changes in the p_H value obtained in the above experiments show, however, that in the presence of a catalytic surface, the photochemical decomposition of even dilute solutions of nitric acid is quite appreciable. It seems reasonable to infer that during the coagulation of a thorium hydroxide sol by light, the colloidal particles of thorium hydroxide exert a similar effect by offering a large catalytic surface and thus considerably promoting the photochemical decomposition of the stabiliser. In this connection certain experiments of Moore and Webster (*Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1913, B 87, 163; *ibid*, 1918, B 90, 169) are interesting. They found that in the absence of certain colloids, like colloidal uranium and ferric hydroxide which act as catalysts for the photochemical synthesis of formaldehyde from carbon dioxide, the reaction either does not go or is too slow to be perceptible.

Silver Sol.

The silver sol prepared by the reduction of a dilute silver nitrate solution by a solution of tannic acid became distinctly alkaline after exposure to ultra-violet light. The stabilising agent in this case is tannic acid; consequently, if the chemical viewpoint be correct, the coagulation in this case must be due to a photochemical decomposition of the tannic acid. To test this experimentally, we have studied the effect of ultra-violet light on tannic acid solutions. An approximately 1% solution of tannic acid was exposed in a quartz tube; to another portion of the same solution a small crystal of potassium nitrate was added, and the resulting solution exposed to ultra-violet light. After an exposure of 24 hours the p_H values of the two exposed solutions were determined and the following data were obtained.

Solution.	p_H .
Tannic acid solution (unexposed) 	3.58
Tannic acid solution (exposed) 	3.56
Tannic acid and potassium nitrate (unexposed) 	3.55
Tannic acid and potassium nitrate (exposed) 	4.60

From the above results it is clear that an aqueous solution of tannic acid by itself is not appreciably decomposed, whereas in the presence of traces of potassium nitrate a considerable decomposition of the tannic acid solution sets in. During the preparation of the above silver sol, a small amount of potassium nitrate is formed (as a result of the addition of potassium carbonate) which induces photochemical changes in the tannic acid solution. This view is supported

by the fact that both in the case of the colloidal silver and in that of a solution of tannic acid containing traces of potassium nitrate, the hydrogen-ion concentrations decrease on exposure.

A further study of the reaction showed that the above decrease in acidity was due to the formation of ammonia. The amount of ammonia actually generated when a solution of tannic acid containing traces of potassium nitrate is exposed to ultra-violet light, was estimated by means of Nessler's reagent. As dilute tannic acid also reacts with Nessler's reagent, the ammonia was distilled off by passing a current of steam, and the amount of ammonia in the distillate was estimated colorimetrically by Folin's micro-Kjeldahl method. A 0.5% solution of tannic acid containing a small amount of potassium nitrate was exposed to the mercury lamp for 24 hours, and 10 c.c. of the exposed solution were treated for the estimation of ammonia. A blank experiment was also performed with a portion of the above tannic acid solution, which had been kept in the dark. 10 C.c. of the above exposed solution were found to contain 0.000125 g. of ammonia.

From the above it is clear that the coagulation of the silver sol is due to the photochemical decomposition of the tannic acid, which is the stabilising agent for this colloid. The photochemical decomposition of tannic acid is not a direct process. The small amount of potassium nitrate present in the system undergoes first a photochemical change which induces the decomposition of tannic acid by light.

Thus in the light of these experiments, the conclusion seems justified that the coagulation of a colloidal solution by light is primarily a photochemical decomposition of the stabilising ions or electrolytes. Further work is in progress.

Summary.

1. A series of colloidal solutions have been exposed to ultra-violet light, and the p_H values, of the clear filtrates obtained before and after exposure, have been measured.

2. By reversing the sign of the charge, a series of oppositely charged sols have been prepared and have been found to coagulate on exposure at about the same rate.

3. The coagulation of a thorium hydroxide sol and the observed changes in the p_H values have been found to be due to the photochemical decomposition of nitric acid, which is the stabilising agent for this sol.

4. An aqueous solution of tannic acid, containing traces of potassium nitrate, has been found to be decomposed on exposure, generating small amounts of ammonia. The coagulation of a silver sol, stabilised by tannic acid, with the development of alkalinity, has been explained on the basis of the above experiment.

5. The experimental results obtained lend considerable support to the view that chemical and photochemical actions are responsible for the coagulation of colloids by light.

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